





PRE-20cl #1



Possible ALL #20, dist = 10.91



Possible ALL #21, dist = 33.76



Possible ALL #33, dist = 48.88



PRE-20cl #2



Possible ALL #15, dist = 36.07



Possible ALL #13, dist = 42.86



Possible ALL #32, dist = 43.37



PRE-20cl #3



Possible ALL #32, dist = 10.09



Possible ALL #34, dist = 21.68



Possible ALL #24, dist = 26.95



PRE-20cl #4



Possible ALL #21, dist = 7.51



Possible ALL #20, dist = 33.11



Possible ALL #33, dist = 43.89



PRE-20cl #5



Possible ALL #24, dist = 13.21



Possible ALL #25, dist = 13.52



Possible ALL #23, dist = 25.8



PRE-20cl #6



Possible ALL #26, dist = 10.91



Possible ALL #25, dist = 22.31



Possible ALL #13, dist = 27.72



PRE-20cl #7



Possible ALL #34, dist = 16.44



Possible ALL #13, dist = 17.09



Possible ALL #26, dist = 19.47



PRE-20cl #8



Possible ALL #26, dist = 24.53



Possible ALL #13, dist = 26.43



Possible ALL #15, dist = 27.51



PRE-20cl #9



Possible ALL #31, dist = 14.74



Possible ALL #15, dist = 32.75



Possible ALL #13, dist = 35.96



PRE-20cl #10



Possible ALL #19, dist = 25.35



Possible ALL #15, dist = 31.86



Possible ALL #9, dist = 39.26



PRE-20cl #11



Possible ALL #9, dist = 20.12



Possible ALL #19, dist = 29.53



Possible ALL #15, dist = 36.29



PRE-20cl #12



Possible ALL #17, dist = 21.08



Possible ALL #16, dist = 53.67



Possible ALL #19, dist = 56.36



PRE-20cl #13



Possible ALL #12, dist = 25.33



Possible ALL #17, dist = 37.06



Possible ALL #39, dist = 49.82



PRE-20cl #14



Possible ALL #13, dist = 18.67



Possible ALL #11, dist = 22.3



Possible ALL #26, dist = 22.45



PRE-20cl #15



Possible ALL #32, dist = 11.49



Possible ALL #13, dist = 14.6



Possible ALL #24, dist = 16.22



PRE-20cl #16



Possible ALL #35, dist = 18.52



Possible ALL #15, dist = 36.37



Possible ALL #13, dist = 43.48



PRE-20cl #17



Possible ALL #37, dist = 5.81



Possible ALL #14, dist = 15.35



Possible ALL #38, dist = 16.92



PRE-20cl #18



Possible ALL #38, dist = 7.01



Possible ALL #37, dist = 18.77



Possible ALL #14, dist = 28.4



PRE-20cl #19



Possible ALL #14, dist = 19.77



Possible ALL #15, dist = 20.39



Possible ALL #13, dist = 22.75



PRE-20cl #20



Possible ALL #40, dist = 3.94



Possible ALL #39, dist = 55.92



Possible ALL #12, dist = 78.66